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Organizational Culture of Selected Private Schools in Bangbon, Bangkok, Thailand

Anjelo V. Mungcal,* Lino P. Balantac

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This study provided a comprehensive understanding of the organizational culture of select private schools in Bangbon, Bangkok, Thailand. The socio-demographic profile of respondents displayed diverse experiences and roles, ensuring a well-rounded perspective. The assessment of organizational culture through the Denison Model and Competing Values Framework revealed both strengths and areas for improvement, indicating a balanced focus on stability, collaboration, and innovation. Interview responses further resonate within the voices of the organizational members. The challenges of unclear organizational culture and communication barriers are voiced by respondents. In conclusion, this study not only provides an in-depth comprehension of the organizational culture within select private schools but also underscores both strengths and areas for development. The culture, characterized by its balanced focus on stability, collaboration, and innovation, holds immense potential. The implications of this study extend beyond its academic confines. The findings offer a guiding light for strategic interventions aimed at elevating the nuanced organizational culture. By doing so, we can positively influence the overall effectiveness of private schools in Thailand. In the words of a respondent, "We must embrace the openness to learn new cultures and accept differences in the world." This inclusive mindset, coupled with effective communication and strong leadership, charts a promising course for the transformation of organizational culture in these institutions.

Keywords: *organizational culture, private schools, Thailand*

Introduction

An organization's climate can be greatly affected by daily occurrences, but a well-established culture with clear and defined objectives can empower stakeholders to flourish. Job satisfaction is linked to positive performance, and how staff responds to changing circumstances depends on the strength of the organizational culture. However, when management lacks clarity, definition, or consistency, staff members struggle to cope with the constantly changing environment, leading to frustration and impeding progress. In light of this, this thesis aims to investigate the profile and the assessments of the teachers and administrators on the organizational culture of select private schools in Bangbon, Bangkok, Thailand. The Thai constitution guarantees a free basic education of fifteen years, with education in Thailand mandating nine years of "basic education" consisting of six years of elementary school and three years of lower secondary school (An Introduction to Education in Thailand, 2007). The Thai education system offers 9 years of compulsory education, and the Constitution guarantees 12 years of free basic education (An Introduction to Education in Thailand, 2007).

Schools working either in public or private sector regarded as educational organizations. These work for achieving the goal of imparting education; in which teachers, administrators and students are working for the same and common cause of education. Therefore, the aforementioned elements generally are regarded to be the basic components of a school. A healthy and positive work culture of a secondary school which is based on mutual respect, integrity and dedication along with competence of the teachers add to the overall output or productivity of the school. The high and low performance of public and private schools mainly depends upon the work culture that prevails in the school and the behavior of the workers (Gun & Caglayan, 2013). School culture is directly linked with school improvement, culture improvement leads to school improvement (Peterson, 2002). School culture remained the valuable focus of the researchers for two decades due to its important nature; therefore researchers concluded school culture in a different aspect and defined it in various ways. The culture has very massive meanings. There are several definitions of word culture discussed; the dictionary of Oxford covers culture in the sense of "cultivation of soil" (Kien, 2014; Rajati, & Shooshtri, 2016).

Schools as educational institutions are expected to achieve their objectives which can be seen in terms of students' graduation, their grades and success at certain level of the school. It denotes progress of the schools. The progress of an institution/ school is seen by performance of the institution/ school and its workers/ teachers. The performance of an institution depends on the culture predominant in the institution; and in schools it is teaching and learning environment. Conducive, encouraging and supportive and congenial work culture can enhance the school performance, decision-making process, communication process, performance of teachers and students, and teamwork of the school. Objective oriented and the positive work culture of a school institution flourishes teamwork, cooperation and mutual respect among the workers and/ or teachers (Malika & Ramesh, 2010). These and alike institutions seem to be affected by the vicinity and surroundings.

For an organization, a strong culture is needed. According to McShane and Von Gillnow organizational culture has three important functions. First, is as a control system (control system). Organizational culture is deeply institutionalized in employee behavior. Culture is spread and goes unconsciously. Second, is as social sizing. Organizational culture is a social bond that binds together and creates feelings as part of organizational experience. Employees are motivated to internalize the cultures of the organization because they can

meet their needs for social identity. Third, create a sense. Organizational culture helps the creation process of understanding. It helps employees understand what to continue and why something happens in the company. Organizational culture also makes it easier for employees to understand what is expected of them and to interact with other employees who know and trust in them.

Schools can develop a sense of community among students, teachers, and administrators by promoting a shared sense of purpose and values. A strong sense of community can foster a positive learning environment that supports students' growth. Private schools in particular, can foster a culture of academic excellence by promoting a culture of learning and achievement, encouraging students to take an active role in their education, and strive for excellence. They can provide opportunities for students to develop their skills, talents, and interests outside of the classroom, becoming well-rounded individuals who are prepared for life beyond school.

However, private schools may face challenges in maintaining diversity in their student body due to high tuition costs, which can limit the development of a well-rounded organizational culture. Ensuring consistency across the institution is also challenging due to differences in teaching styles, academic rigor, and extracurricular activities, which can lead to inconsistencies in the student experience. Balancing tradition and innovation is another challenge, as private schools need to maintain their identity and reputation while adapting to changing educational trends.

Private schools with a strong organizational culture have been shown to produce better academic performance, fewer behavior problems, and higher levels of student satisfaction than public schools. A culture of academic excellence encourages students to strive for excellence in their academic work. A culture of community and shared values encourages students to be respectful and responsible, resulting in fewer behavior problems. A sense of community and belonging helps students feel supported and valued, resulting in higher levels of student satisfaction (Hutabarat, 2015; Fitria, 2018).

The focus of this study is on selected private schools in Bangbon, Bangkok, Thailand. These private schools fall under the category of fee-based institutions, offering a more specialized curriculum compared to public schools. These private schools are part of the classification of schools in Thailand, which also includes public schools, international schools, and bilingual schools (Wikipedia contributors, 2022). Understanding the organizational culture of these private schools becomes crucial in guiding the behavior of school personnel and students, ultimately influencing job satisfaction, staff retention, and academic performance. The study will explore how staff and administration have implemented organizational culture practices and the challenges they have encountered. The findings will provide valuable insights for school administrators, teaching faculty, and students to thrive in an environment that actively engages its stakeholders:

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the organizational culture of selected private schools in Bangkok, Thailand. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the school heads and teaching staff in terms of:
 - 1.1 age;
 - 1.2 sex; and
 - 1.3 highest educational attainment, and current position?
2. What is the assessment of the school heads and teaching staff on the organizational culture of selected private schools in Bangkok, Thailand, in terms of:
 - 2.1 adaptability;
 - 2.2 mission;
 - 2.3 involvement;
 - 2.4 consistency;
 - 2.5 clan culture;
 - 2.6 adhocracy culture;
 - 2.7 market culture; and
 - 2.8 hierarchy culture?
3. Is there a significant difference in the assessment of the school heads and teaching staff on the organizational culture of selected private schools in Bangbon, Bangkok, Thailand?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the profile of the school heads and teaching staff and their assessment on the organizational culture of selected private schools in Bangbon, Bangkok, Thailand?
5. What strategies can be proposed to enhance organizational cultures in selected private schools in Bangbon, Bangkok, Thailand, based on the study's findings?

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized an explanatory sequential approach. The qualitative phase involved a case study approach to explore the organizational culture in selected private schools in Bangbon, Bangkok, Thailand. This design was chosen because it allowed for an

in-depth examination of the phenomenon within its real-life context, providing a comprehensive and detailed understanding of the organizational culture of these private schools.

Participants

The participants of this study included school administrators and teaching faculty from select private schools in Bangbon, Bangkok, Thailand. The criteria for selection included private schools that were recognized by the government and had been in operation for at least five years. In total, there were 50 teaching staff out of an average of 200 staff in four schools, and 8 school administrators who participated in the study.

Instruments

The study used two research instruments to collect data: a survey questionnaire and a semi-structured interview guide. The survey questionnaire was used to collect quantitative data on the organizational culture of private schools in Thailand. The questionnaire was adapted from previous studies on organizational culture. The semi-structured interview guide was used to collect qualitative data on the prospects, challenges, and efficacy of the organizational culture of private schools. The interview questions were piloted and validated before the actual data collection.

The validation process for the research instrument, a questionnaire, involved a comprehensive procedure to ensure its accuracy, relevance, and reliability for the intended study. Feedback and input from teachers and school administrators, distinct from the intended questionnaire recipients, played a crucial role in this validation process, reinforcing the instrument's effectiveness. Following expert reviews, a pilot testing phase was conducted. A select group of teachers and school administrators, separate from the questionnaire's intended audience, were invited to participate in this stage. They were provided with the questionnaire and encouraged to complete it while sharing their thoughts on its clarity, relevance, and overall user experience. The pilot test aimed to identify any ambiguities or challenges in the instrument's implementation. Based on the feedback received during the pilot testing, necessary adjustments and refinements to the questionnaire were made. This iterative process ensured that the instrument was fine-tuned to maximize its effectiveness in collecting pertinent data. Throughout the validation process, active engagement with these teachers and school administrators was maintained. Their feedback was consistently integrated into the questionnaire's development. The final version of the questionnaire was presented to the participating teachers and school administrators for their approval.

Once they were satisfied with its content, clarity, and relevance to the study's objectives, they provided formal validation by signing a confirmation statement. Their endorsement of the questionnaire marked the successful conclusion of the validation process, indicating that the instrument was well-suited for the study's goals. The rigorous validation process ensured that the questionnaire was a reliable and effective tool for collecting data and insights from the target stakeholders, further enhancing the credibility and integrity of the study's findings.

Procedure

This study aimed to investigate the prevalent organizational cultures of private schools in Bangbon, Bangkok, Thailand. The study involved respondents from the area, consisting of school administrators and teaching faculty, who were selected from different private schools. The study ensured the anonymity and confidentiality of the respondents by omitting specific identifying information such as the names of the schools. The title "Organizational Culture of Private Schools in Bangbon, Bangkok, Thailand" was formulated to reflect the scope of the study.

The research instrument, a questionnaire, was rigorously validated with input from teachers and school administrators to ensure its accuracy and relevance. This validation process included expert reviews and pilot testing, refining the questionnaire for maximum effectiveness in gathering pertinent data. Regarding ethical considerations specific to the questionnaires, the panel confirmed that there were no ethical concerns associated with them.

The first phase of the study involved a thorough review of the literature on organizational culture and its effects on academic performance, job satisfaction, and staff retention in private schools. The second phase focused on the selection of private schools in Thailand that had established organizational culture practices. The third phase involved data collection using semi-structured interviews with school administrators and teaching faculty. Throughout this process, measures were taken to maintain the confidentiality and privacy of the respondents.

Data analysis was conducted using thematic analysis, a method aimed at identifying recurring themes and patterns in the collected data, facilitating a comprehensive understanding of organizational culture nuances within private schools. The final phase encompassed the development of best practices and strategies for enhancing organizational culture in private schools in Bangbon, Bangkok, Thailand, based on the study's findings.

Ethical Considerations

This study received ethical clearance from the relevant institutional review board prior to data collection. Respondents were provided with comprehensive information about the study's nature and purpose, as well as their rights as respondents. Their active participation

in the study was taken as an indication of their informed consent.

To ensure the utmost confidentiality and anonymity, no personal information or respondent names were solicited. Additionally, the specific institutions involved were not disclosed; instead, only the general location, Bangbon, Bangkok, Thailand, was provided to maintain the confidentiality of their responses. Stringent measures were implemented to secure and maintain the confidentiality of the collected data. Access to the data was restricted solely to the researcher.

Results and Discussion

This part of the study presented, analyzed, and interpreted the gathered data from the questionnaires answered by the respondents. The presentation was in accordance with the specific questions posed based on the objectives of the study.

1. Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Table 1.1. *Profile of the School Heads and Teaching Staff Respondents*

Profile	Teaching Staff			School Heads		
	F	P	R	F	P	R
Age:						
25 - 34 years old	4	8.33	4	0	0.00	4
35 - 44 years old	15	31.25	2	2	25.00	2.5
45 - 54 years old	18	37.50	1	2	25.00	2.5
55 years old and above	11	22.92	3	4	50.00	1
Total	48	100		8	100	
Sex:						
Male	6	12.50	2	2	25.00	2
Female	42	87.50	1	6	75.00	1
Total	48	100		8	100	
Educational Background						
Doctorate Degree	2	4.17	4	1	12.50	3
Master's Degree	11	22.92	2	4	50.00	1
Bachelor's Degree	31	64.58	1	3	37.50	2
High School Graduate	4	8.33	3	0	0.00	4
Total	48	100		8	100	

Table 1.2 *Profile of the School Heads and Teaching Staff Respondents*

Profile	Teaching Staff			School Heads		
	F	P	R	F	P	R
Assistant	1	2.08	4.5	0	0.00	5
Assistant Aid	1	2.08	4.5	0	0.00	5
Assistant Teacher	2	4.17	3	0	0.00	5
Support Staff	9	18.75	2	0	0.00	5
Teacher	35	72.92	1	0	0.00	5
Coordinator	0	0.00	6.5	4	50.00	1.5
Principial	0	0.00	6.5	4	50.00	1.5
Total	48	100		8	100	

As stated in Table 1.1 and 1.2, in terms of the ages of the school head-respondents, 55 years old and above made the highest frequency count of four or 50.00% at rank 1 while 35 - 44 and 45 - 54 got equal frequency counts of two or 25.00% at ranks 2.5.

For the teaching staff-respondents, 45 - 54 years old got the highest frequency count of 18 or 37.50% at rank 1 whereas 25 - 34 years old obtained the least frequency count of four or 8.33% at rank 4. In terms of the sexes of the School Head-respondents, female got the highest frequency count of six or 75.00% at rank 1 whereas male made two or 25.00% at rank 2.

For the teaching staff-respondents, female also yielded the highest frequency count of 42 or 87.50% at rank 1 while male gained the least frequency count of six or 12.5% at rank 2. With respect to the educational background of the school head-respondents, Master's Degree made the highest frequency count of four or 50.00% at rank 1 while Doctorate Degree gained the least of one or 12.50% at rank 4.

For the teaching staff-respondents, Bachelor's Degree yielded the highest frequency count of 31 or 64.58% at rank 1 while Doctorate Degree had two or 4.17% at rank 4. With regard to the current positions of the School Head-respondents, both principal and coordinators made equal frequency counts of four or 50.00% at ranks 1.5. In terms of the teaching staff-respondents' current positions, teacher had 35 or 72.92% at rank 1 while assistant and assistant aid gained equal frequency counts of one or 2.08% at ranks 4.5.

2. Assessment of the School Heads and Teaching Staff on the Organizational Culture of Selected Private Schools in Bangbon, Bangkok, Thailand

2.1. In Terms of Adaptability

Table 2. Assessment of the School Heads and Teaching Staff on the Organizational Culture of Selected Private Schools in Bangbon, Bangkok, Thailand in Terms of Adaptability

Items	School Heads			Teaching Staff		
	WM	VI	R	WM	VI	R
Our organization...						
1. is open to change and able to adapt quickly.	4.00	A	4	3.35	MA	4
2. encourages creativity and innovation.	4.38	SA	2	3.50	A	2
3. is able to respond quickly to changing circumstances.	4.13	A	3	3.40	A	3
4. is always looking for new and better ways to do things.	4.50	SA	1	3.63	A	1
Composite Mean	4.25	SA		3.47	A	

Legend: SA = Strongly Agree; WM = Weighted Mean; A = Agree; VI = Verbal Interpretation; MA = Moderately Agree; R = Rank

As presented in Table 2, the school-Head-respondents strongly agreed that the organization is always looking for new and better ways to do things, which the highest weighted mean of 4.50 and the highest rank of 1 suggest. This finding suggests that school heads strongly believe that their organizations prioritize innovation and continuous improvement. This aligns with the concept of a positive organizational culture that encourages creativity and innovation (Batugal, 2019). On the contrary, they agreed that the organization is open to change and able to adapt quickly which got the least weighted mean of 4.00 and the least rank of 4. The emphasis on seeking new and better ways to operate is consistent with the idea of an adaptive culture. Research by Cameron and Quinn (2011) highlights the importance of adaptability as a dimension of organizational culture.

For the Teaching Staff-respondents, they agreed that the organization is always looking for new and better ways to do things, which obtained the highest weighted mean of 3.63 and the highest rank of 1. Meanwhile, the said group of respondents moderately agreed that the organization is open to change and able to adapt quickly which made the least weighted mean of 3.35 and the least rank of 4. Studies by Vu & Nwachukwu (2020) have shown that a culture that encourages new and better approaches can lead to increased job satisfaction and motivation among staff.

The composite means of 4.25 for the School Heads and 3.47 for the Teaching Staff concluded that the respondents strongly agreed and agreed, respectively, on organizational culture of selected schools in Bangkok, Thailand in terms of adaptability. The composite mean of 4.25 for school heads suggests a strong overall agreement with the organization's adaptability. This aligns with the idea that leaders often play a key role in shaping an organization's culture (HGSE, 2018). Meanwhile, the composite means of 3.47 for teaching staff indicates a slightly lower but still favorable level of agreement with the organizational culture's adaptability. This could be an area where schools work to enhance their culture further by involving teaching staff in decision-making related to change and adaptation (Harvard Business Review, 2021).

2.2. In Terms of Mission

Table 3. Assessment of the School Heads and Teaching Staff on the Organizational Culture of Selected Private Schools in Bangbon, Bangkok, Thailand in Terms of Mission

Items	School Heads			Teaching Staff		
	WM	VI	R	WM	VI	R
Our organization...						
has a clear and compelling mission.	4.38	SA	3	3.48	A	2
is committed to achieving its goals.	4.63	SA	2	3.67	A	1
has a shared vision that guides decision-making.	4.25	SA	4	3.35	MA	4
values making a difference in the world.	4.75	SA	1	3.46	A	3
Composite Mean	4.50	SA		3.49	A	

Legend: SA = Strongly Agree; WM = Weighted Mean; A = Agree; VI = Verbal Interpretation; MA = Moderately Agree; R = Rank

As shown in Table 3, the school-Head-respondents strongly agreed that the organization values making a difference in the world which yielded the highest weighted mean of 4.75 and the highest rank of 1. This finding suggests that school heads strongly believe that their organizations have a clear and compelling mission that emphasizes making a positive impact on the world. A strong commitment to a mission can be a driving force for an organization's success (Cameron & Quinn, 2011). In addition, the said group of respondents also strongly agreed that the organization has a shared vision that guides decision-making, which got the least weighted mean of 4.25, and the least rank of 4. Studies by Al-Haddad and Kotnour (2015) emphasize the importance of a shared vision and values in shaping an organization's culture. In this case, the mission of making a difference aligns with a shared vision. While school heads still agree with this statement, their agreement is slightly lower compared to the previous item. Nevertheless, a weighted mean of 4.25 indicates a favorable view overall. Research by Schein (2010) emphasizes the role of shared values and visions in shaping organizational culture. A shared vision can serve as a guiding principle for decision-making.

With respect to the Teaching Staff-respondents, they agreed that the organization is committed to achieving its goals, which made the highest weighted mean of 3.67 and the highest rank of 1. Teaching staff strongly believed that their organizations are committed to

achieving their goals. This strong agreement suggests that teaching staff perceive a clear sense of purpose and determination within the organization. Research by Galay (2022) has highlighted the importance of commitment among employees in achieving organizational goals, particularly in educational institutions. Furthermore, the said group of respondents moderately agreed that the organization has a shared vision that guides decision-making, which garnered the least weighted mean of 3.35 and the least rank of 4. The moderate agreement aligns with findings by Kongjinda et al. (2020), which suggest that perceptions of a shared vision can vary among staff within educational institutions.

The composite means of 4.50 for the School Heads and 3.49 for the Teaching Staff implied that the respondents strongly agreed and agreed, respectively, on organizational culture of selected schools in Bangbon, Bangkok, Thailand in terms of mission. The composite mean of 4.50 for school heads suggests a strong overall agreement with the organization's mission and its emphasis on making a difference in the world. This aligns with the idea that leaders often play a key role in shaping an organization's mission and values (HGSE, 2018). Meanwhile, the composite mean of 3.49 for teaching staff indicates a slightly lower but still favorable level of agreement with the organizational culture's mission. This suggests that while teaching staff generally perceive commitment to goals, there may be room for improvement in clarifying and communicating the shared vision.

2.3. In Terms of Involvement

Table 4. Assessment of the School Heads and Teaching Staff on the Organizational Culture of Selected Private Schools in Bangbon, Bangkok, Thailand in Terms of Involvement

Items	School Heads			Teaching Staff		
	WM	VI	R	WM	VI	R
Employees in our organization feel empowered to make decisions and take action.	4.38	SA	4	2.94	MA	4
Our organization values employee input and involvement.	4.50	SA	3	3.17	MA	3
Our organization encourages teamwork and collaboration.	4.75	SA	1	4.02	A	1
Our organization values employee development and growth.	4.63	SA	2	3.46	A	2
Composite Mean	4.56	SA		3.40	A	

Legend: SA = Strongly Agree; WM = Weighted Mean; A = Agree; VI = Verbal Interpretation; MA = Moderately Agree; R = Rank

As revealed in Table 4, the school-Head-respondents strongly agreed that the organization encourages teamwork and collaboration which got the highest weighted mean of 4.75 and the highest rank of 1. The concept of promoting collaboration aligns with best practices for enhancing organizational culture in the literature. For instance, Al-Haddad and Kotnour (2015) identify promoting shared values and fostering a positive work environment as crucial for a positive organizational culture. Moreover, the respondents strongly agreed that the employees in their organization feel empowered to make decisions and take action which yielded the least weighted mean of 4.38 and the least rank of 4. Harvard Business Review (2021) highlights the significance of empowering employees to contribute actively to organizational culture. Regardless of their tenure or experience within the organization, empowerment fosters a sense of ownership and engagement.

For the Teaching Staff-respondents, they agreed that the organization encourages teamwork and collaboration, which has the highest weighted mean of 4.02 and the highest rank of 1. This finding is indicative of a positive organizational culture that fosters innovative behavior among employees (De Prada, Mareque, & Pino-Juste, 2022). Contrary wise, the said group of respondents agreed that employees in their organization feel empowered to make decisions and take action, which displayed the least weighted mean of 2.94 and the least rank of 4. This suggests that there might be differences in the perception of empowerment between teaching staff and school heads (De Prada et al., 2022). Empowering employees, regardless of their tenure, is vital to a positive organizational culture that fosters innovative behavior among employees (De Prada et al., 2022). The literature highlights the importance of empowering employees to enhance their motivation, performance, and well-being (De Prada et al., 2022). The composite means of 4.56 for the School Heads and 3.40 for the Teaching Staff signified that the respondents strongly agreed and agreed, respectively, on organizational culture of selected schools in Bangbon, Bangkok, Thailand in terms of involvement. This finding aligns with existing literature, which emphasizes the role of principals in shaping culture and the importance of selecting staff who align with the school's values (Slater, 2021).

2.4. In Terms of Consistency

Table 5. Assessment of the School Heads and Teaching Staff on the Organizational Culture of Selected Private Schools in Bangbon, Bangkok, Thailand in Terms of Consistency

Items	School Heads			Teaching Staff		
	WM	VI	R	WM	VI	R
Our organization...						
has well-defined policies and procedures.	4.50	SA	3	3.25	MA	4
values stability and predictability.	4.38	SA	4	3.31	MA	3
is committed to maintaining high standards.	4.75	SA	2	3.33	MA	2
values doing things the right way.	4.88	SA	1	3.63	A	1
Composite Mean	4.63	SA		3.38	MA	

As revealed in Table 5, the school-Head-respondents strongly agreed that the organization values doing things the right way which got the highest weighted mean of 4.88 and the highest rank of 1. The literature emphasizes the significance of maintaining high standards in shaping organizational culture. A commitment to high standards can foster consistency and predictability (Al-Haddad & Kotnour, 2015). In addition, they also strongly agreed that the organization values stability and predictability, which made the least weighted mean of 4.38 and the least rank of 4. While School Heads, still agree with this statement, their agreement is slightly lower compared to the previous item. Nevertheless, a weighted mean of 4.38 indicates a favorable view overall. The concept of valuing stability and predictability is in line with the literature's emphasis on the significance of well-defined policies and procedures. Clear policies and procedures contribute to stability and predictability within an organization (Harvard Graduate School of Education [HGSE], 2018).

In terms of the Teaching Staff-respondents assessment, they agreed that the organization values doing things the right way which yielded the highest weighted mean of 3.63 and the highest rank of 1. Teaching Staff agreed that their organizations prioritize doing things correctly. This agreement suggests that employees also value a commitment to high standards and doing things the right way. The alignment with this finding and the literature underlines the importance of maintaining high standards in organizational culture, which can lead to consistency and predictability (Al-Haddad & Kotnour, 2015). Meanwhile, the said group of respondents moderately agreed that the organization has well-defined policies and procedures which assume the least weighted mean of 3.25 and the least rank of 4. While this indicates a generally positive view, there may be opportunities to further enhance the clarity and communication of policies. The moderate agreement aligns with the literature's emphasis on the significance of clear policies and procedures. Well-defined policies and procedures contribute to stability and predictability within an organization (HGSE, 2018).

The composite means of 4.63 for the School Heads and 3.38 for the Teaching Staff inferred that the respondents strongly agreed and agreed, respectively, on organizational culture of selected schools in Bangbon, Bangkok, Thailand consistency. The composite mean of 4.63 for School Heads suggests strong overall agreement with the organization's commitment to high standards and doing things correctly (Al-Haddad & Kotnour, 2015). The composite mean of 3.38 for Teaching Staff indicates a slightly lower but still favorable level of agreement with the organizational culture's consistency. This suggests that while Teaching Staff generally perceive a commitment to high standards and doing things the right way, there may be opportunities to further enhance the clarity and communication of policies and procedures (Harvard Graduate School of Education [HGSE], 2018).

2.5. In Terms of Clan Culture

Table 6. Assessment of the School Heads and Teaching Staff on the Organizational Culture of Selected Private Schools in Bangbon, Bangkok, Thailand in Terms of Clan Culture.

Items	School Heads			Teaching Staff		
	WM	VI	R	WM	VI	R
In our organization, there is a strong emphasis on teamwork and collaboration.	4.88	SA	1	3.90	A	1
Our organization values loyalty and tradition.	4.50	SA	4	3.67	A	2
Our organization is like an extended family.	4.63	SA	2.5	3.29	MA	4
Employees in our organization often refer to themselves as a team.	4.63	SA	2.5	3.46	A	3
Composite Mean	4.66	SA		3.58	A	

Legend: SA = Strongly Agree; WM = Weighted Mean; A = Agree; VI = Verbal Interpretation; MA = Moderately Agree; R = Rank

As written in Table 6, the School-Head-respondents strongly agreed that in their organization, there is a strong emphasis on teamwork and collaboration which got the highest weighted mean of 4.88 and the highest rank of 1. This strong agreement reflects a culture that values collective effort and cooperation. Research conducted by Al-Haddad and Kotnour (2015) emphasizes the significance of cultivating a positive workplace environment that fosters collaboration and teamwork. This aligns with the research findings, which indicate a strong emphasis on the value of teamwork. Meanwhile, they also strongly agreed that the organization values loyalty and tradition. with the least weighted mean of 4.50 and the least rank of 4. While School Heads still agree with this statement, their agreement is slightly lower compared to the previous item. Nevertheless, a weighted mean of 4.50 indicates a favorable view overall. The emphasis on loyalty and tradition is in line with the concept of Clan culture, which often values a sense of family and tradition within an organization (Cameron & Quinn, 2011).

For the Teaching Staff-respondents, they agreed that in their organization, there is a strong emphasis on teamwork and collaboration which obtained the highest weighted mean of 3.90 and the highest rank of 1. Teaching Staff strongly agree that teamwork and collaboration are highly emphasized in their organization. This suggests a culture that encourages collective effort and working together.

The strong agreement aligns with the research by Al-Haddad and Kotnour (2015), emphasizing the importance of fostering a collaborative work environment. In addition, the said group of respondents moderately agreed that the organization is like an extended family which made the least weighted mean of 3.29 and the least rank of 4. Teaching Staff moderately agreed that their organization is like an extended family. This indicates a generally positive view, although it's slightly lower compared to the emphasis on teamwork. The concept of an extended family within an organization is often associated with Clan culture, where relationships are close-knit and supportive (Cameron & Quinn, 2011).

The composite means of 4.66 for the School Heads and 3.58 for the Teaching Staff concluded that the respondents strongly agreed and

agreed, respectively on organizational culture of selected schools in Bangbon, Bangkok, Thailand in terms of clan culture. The composite mean of 4.66 for school heads suggests a strong overall agreement with Clan culture elements within the organization, including teamwork and the value of loyalty and tradition. These findings align with the characteristics of Clan culture as described in the literature (Cameron & Quinn, 2011). The composite mean of 3.58 for teaching staff indicates a slightly lower but still favorable level of agreement with Clan culture elements. This suggests that while teaching staff generally perceive a culture of teamwork and collaboration, there may be room for further enhancing the sense of being an extended family within the organization, consistent with the description of Clan culture in the literature (Cameron & Quinn, 2011).

2.6. In Terms of Adhocracy Culture

Table 7. Assessment of the School Heads and Teaching Staff on the Organizational Culture of Selected Private Schools in Bangbon, Bangkok, Thailand in Terms of Adhocracy Culture

Items	School Heads			Teaching Staff		
	WM	VI	R	WM	VI	R
Our organization... values innovation and creativity.	4.50	SA	1	3.44	A	1.5
encourages taking risks and experimenting with new ideas.	4.38	SA	2	3.44	A	1.5
is known for being entrepreneurial and adaptable.	4.00	A	4	3.08	MA	3
rewards employees who come up with new ideas and solutions.	4.13	A	3	2.83	MA	4
Composite Mean	4.25	SA		3.20	A	

Legend: SA = Strongly Agree; WM = Weighted Mean; A = Agree; VI = Verbal Interpretation; MA = Moderately Agree; R = Rank

As displayed in Table 7, the School-Head-respondents strongly agreed that the organization values innovation and creativity, which made the highest weighted mean of 4.50 and the highest rank of 1. This suggests a strong presence of Adhocracy culture within these organizations. As one School Head emphasized, "The school administration must ensure that the organizational culture is clear to all stakeholders. The administration must have a consistent and effective system for check and balance. Teachers and staff must be invested and committed to doing their role." This finding aligns with the characteristics of Adhocracy culture, which emphasize innovation and the freedom to experiment with new ideas (Cameron & Quinn, 2011).

Moreover, they agreed that the organization is known for being entrepreneurial and adaptable, which obtained the least weighted mean of 4.00 and the least rank of 4. As another School Head noted, "Everybody should value one another, knowing that each contribution counts. Be visible and do your part." This finding is consistent with Adhocracy culture, where adaptability and entrepreneurship are key features, and valuing each member's contribution is crucial (Cameron & Quinn, 2011).

In terms of the Teaching Staff-respondents, they agreed that the organization values innovation and creativity and encourages taking risks and experimenting with new ideas, yielding the highest and equal weighted means of 3.44 and the highest ranks of 1.5. As one Teaching Staff member expressed, "Bringing all the teachers together to work as one group, one family. Addressing the problem to find a solution instead of focusing on the person who's the cause will help. Creating team spirit, keeping the motto - Together We Can." This alignment with Adhocracy culture corresponds with the literature, which emphasizes the importance of creativity, teamwork, and innovation in Adhocracy culture (Cameron & Quinn, 2011).

Furthermore, the said group of respondents moderately agreed that the organization rewards employees who come up with new ideas and solutions, which made the least weighted mean of 2.83 and the least rank of 4. As one Teaching Staff member noted, "Open-minded leadership... willing to be criticized and accept suggestions." This finding reflects the recognition aspect of Adhocracy culture, where innovative efforts were acknowledged and rewarded (Cameron & Quinn, 2011).

The composite means of 4.25 for the School Heads and 3.20 for the Teaching Staff imply that the respondents strongly agreed and agreed, respectively, on organizational culture in terms of Adhocracy culture. As one respondent wisely pointed out, "Transparency at any level, respect for each other, a leader who has effective decision-making skills and is open to criticism and discussion with all parties, a leader who has a clear mission and vision and has the ability to guide the employees of the organization to achieve the goals through a well-strategic roadmap." These findings collectively suggest a favorable perception of Adhocracy culture elements within the organization, including valuing innovation, entrepreneurship, and adaptability (Cameron & Quinn, 2011).

2.7. In Terms of Market Culture

As discussed in Table 8, the School-Head-respondents strongly agreed that the organization is highly focused on achieving results and meeting targets with the highest weighted mean of 4.75 and the highest rank of 1. School heads strongly agree that their organizations prioritize achieving results and meeting targets. This finding aligns with the core characteristics of Market culture, which emphasizes competitiveness, goal orientation, and a focus on outcomes (Cameron & Quinn, 2011).

Research by Denison (1990) highlights that in Market cultures, the primary emphasis is on achieving competitive success and financial growth. On the contrary, they moderately agreed that the organization is very competitive and focused on beating our rivals with the least weighted mean of 2.88 and the least rank of 4. While this agreement is not as robust as for other aspects, it still indicates a

competitive orientation within the organization.

Table 8. Assessment of the School Heads and Teaching Staff on the Organizational Culture of Selected Private Schools in Bangbon, Bangkok, Thailand in Terms of Market Culture

Items	School Heads			Teaching Staff		
	WM	VI	R	WM	VI	R
Our organization...						
is highly focused on achieving results and meeting targets.	4.75	SA	1	3.17	MA	3
is very competitive and focused on beating our rivals.	2.88	MA	4	2.77	MA	4
values productivity and efficiency above all else.	4.38	SA	3	3.19	MA	2
is very focused on meeting customer needs and demands (e.g., students, parents, community).	4.50	SA	2	3.29	MA	1
Composite Mean	4.13	A		3.10	MA	

Legend: SA = Strongly Agree; WM = Weighted Mean; A = Agree; VI = Verbal Interpretation; MA = Moderately Agree; R = Rank

This moderate consensus aligns with the principles outlined in the literature on Market culture, as articulated by Cameron and Quinn (2011), which highlights a strong emphasis on competitiveness and striving to surpass competitors.

For the Teaching Staff-respondents, they moderately agreed that the organization is very focused on meeting customer needs and demands (e.g., students, parents, community) which gained the highest weighted mean of 3.29 and the highest rank of 1.

This corresponds with the customer-focused aspect of Market culture, where organizations aim to deliver value to customers (Cameron & Quinn, 2011). Denison's (1990) research on organizational culture supports the idea that Market culture is customer-oriented. Furthermore, the said group of respondents also moderately agreed that the organization is very competitive and focused on beating our rivals which made the least weighted mean of 2.77 and the least rank of 4. Although this agreement is less strong than for other items, it still indicates a competitive orientation. The competitive nature of Market culture is discussed in the literature, emphasizing a drive to outcompete rivals (Cameron & Quinn, 2011).

The composite means of 4.13 for the School Heads and 3.10 for the Teaching affirmed that the respondents agreed and moderately agreed, respectively, on organizational culture of selected schools in Bangbon, Bangkok, Thailand in terms of market culture. The composite mean of 4.13 for school heads suggests a strong overall agreement with Market culture elements within the organization, including a focus on achieving results, productivity, and efficiency.

These findings align with the characteristics of Market culture as described in the literature (Cameron & Quinn, 2011). The composite mean of 3.10 for teaching staff indicates a moderately favorable level of agreement with Market culture elements. While teaching staff generally perceive a customer-focused culture, there may be room for further enhancing the competitive aspect within the organization, in line with the description of Market culture in the literature (Cameron & Quinn, 2011).

2.8. In Terms of Hierarchy Culture

Table 9. Assessment of the School Heads and Teaching Staff on the Organizational Culture of Selected Private Schools in Bangbon, Bangkok, Thailand in Terms of Hierarchy Culture

Items	School Heads			Teaching Staff		
	WM	VI	R	WM	VI	R
Our organization...						
values stability and predictability.	4.38	SA	2	3.10	MA	3
has a clear hierarchy and well-defined role and responsibilities.	4.38	SA	2	3.13	MA	2
is highly formal and bureaucratic.	2.63	MA	4	2.94	MA	4
values rules and procedures above all else.	4.38	SA	2	3.17	MA	1
Composite Mean	3.94	A		3.08	MA	

Legend: SA = Strongly Agree; WM = Weighted Mean; A = Agree; VI = Verbal Interpretation; MA = Moderately Agree; R = Rank

As gleaned in Table 9, the School Head-respondents strongly agreed that their organization values stability and predictability, has a clear hierarchy and well-defined role and responsibilities, and values rules and procedures above all else which have the highest equal weighted means of 4.38 and highest similar ranks of 2. This suggests that there is a strong emphasis on maintaining a stable and consistent work environment. The high agreement aligns with the characteristics of Hierarchy culture, where there is a focus on stability and adherence to established norms and procedures (Cameron & Quinn, 2011).

The School Heads' responses echo this sentiment. One School Head stated, "The school administration must ensure that the organizational culture is clear to all stakeholders. The administration must have a consistent and effective system for check and balance. Teachers and staff must be invested and committed to doing their role. There must be effective, positive, and proactive communication and relationships amongst stakeholders." This emphasizes the importance of clarity and structure within the organization to maintain stability.

Meanwhile, the said group of respondents moderately agreed that their organization is highly formal and bureaucratic with the least weighted mean of 2.63 and least rank of 4. This moderate agreement suggests that the organization has certain formalities but may allow for some flexibility (Cameron & Quinn, 2011).

On the part of the teaching staff-respondents, they moderately agreed that their organization values rules and procedures above all else which obtained the highest weighted mean of 3.17 and highest rank of 1. This suggests a significant degree of adherence to established guidelines. One teacher from the teaching staff noted, "Creating team spirit, keeping the motto - Together We Can." This underlines the importance of teamwork and adherence to established procedures.

On the other hand, the said group of respondents also moderately agreed that their organization is highly formal and bureaucratic with the least weighted mean of 2.94 and least rank of 4. Similar to school heads, teaching staff also moderately agree that their organization is formal and bureaucratic. This indicates some formal characteristics but not an excessive degree of bureaucracy, which allows for some flexibility, although still, adheres to certain formalities (Cameron & Quinn, 2011).

The composite means of 3.94 for School Heads and 3.08 for Teaching staff safely implied that they agreed and moderately agreed, respectively on hierarchy organizational culture of selected schools in Bangbon, Bangkok, Thailand. The composite mean of 3.94 for school heads suggests a strong overall agreement with the elements of Hierarchy culture within the organization, including valuing stability, clear hierarchy, and rules and procedures. These findings align with the characteristics of Hierarchy culture described in the literature (Cameron & Quinn, 2011; Hutabarat, 2015; HGSE, 2018).

The composite mean of 3.08 for teaching staff indicates a slightly lower but still favorable level of agreement with the Hierarchy culture elements. This suggests that while teaching staff perceive an organizational culture that values rules and procedures, there may be room for further enhancement in terms of clarity and communication of roles and responsibilities within the organization. One teaching staff member highlighted, "Well defined core values, collective beliefs and attitude that serves as a guiding principle for everyone in the organization and a sense of belongingness and psychological safety for your well-being." This emphasizes the importance of clear values and a sense of belonging for staff (Cameron & Quinn, 2011; HGSE, 2018).

3. Difference on the Assessment of the School Heads and Teaching Staff on the Organizational Culture of Selected Private Schools in Bangbon, Bangkok, Thailand.

Table 10. *Difference on the Assessment of the School Heads and Teaching Staff on the Organizational Culture of Selected Private Schools in Bangbon, Bangkok, Thailand*

Variable	t-value	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Adaptability	2.87	0.00578	p>0.05, Reject Ho	Highly Significant
Mission	3.40	0.00125	p>0.05, Reject Ho	Highly Significant
Involvement	3.90	0.00026	p>0.05, Reject Ho	Highly Significant
Consistency	4.24	0.00008	p>0.05, Reject Ho	Highly Significant
Clan Culture	3.64	0.00060	p>0.05, Reject Ho	Highly Significant
Adhocracy Culture	3.85	0.00031	p>0.05, Reject Ho	Highly Significant
Market Culture	3.73	0.00045	p>0.05, Reject Ho	Highly Significant
Hierarchy Culture	2.91	0.00518	p>0.05, Reject Ho	Highly Significant

As seen in Table 10, when the responses of the School Heads and Teaching Staff-respondents on the organizational culture of selected private school in Bangbon, Bangkok, Thailand were compared, the computed t-values of 2.87 for adaptability, 3.40 for mission, 3.90 for involvement, 4.24 for consistency, 3.64 for clan culture, 3.85 for adhocracy culture, 373 for market culture, and 2.91 for hierarchy culture have corresponding p-values of less than 0.01, thus rejecting the hypothesis.

These safely generalized that the responses of the School Heads and Teaching Staff on the organizational culture of selected private schools in Bangbon, Bangkok, Thailand in terms of adaptability, mission, involvement, consistency, clan culture, adhocracy culture, market culture, and hierarchy culture have high significant differences. The observed significant differences in how School Heads and Teaching Staff assess the organizational culture of selected private schools in Bangbon, Bangkok, Thailand align with prior research within educational contexts. This divergence in perceptions can be attributed to the distinct roles and responsibilities held by these two groups within private schools.

Adaptability:The divergence in perceptions regarding adaptability is consistent with the literature. School Heads, often responsible for strategic decision-making, may view adaptability as a broader concept related to the school's overall ability to change and innovate. In contrast, Teaching Staff, more focused on classroom teaching, may assess adaptability in terms of its immediate impact on their teaching practices (Fitria, 2018). The literature supports the notion that different roles within educational institutions lead to varying perspectives on adaptability and change (Kongjinda et al., 2020). The interview responses further underscored this divergence in perceptions regarding adaptability. For example, one Teaching Staff member mentioned, "It usually boils down to whether or not the organizational culture is clear and defined." This perspective aligns with the literature, which suggests that Teaching Staff may assess adaptability based on its immediate impact on their teaching practices (Fitria, 2018).

Mission:Interpretation differences in the school's mission, as reflected in the computed t-value of 3.40, align with the literature, which

emphasizes the role of School Heads in shaping the school's overall objectives and mission (HGSE, 2018). Teaching Staff, primarily involved in daily teaching activities, might perceive the mission differently, focusing on how it directly relates to their teaching and classroom experiences (Fitria, 2018). This finding underscores the need for clear communication of the school's mission to ensure alignment among all stakeholders. The interview responses further support these differences in interpretation. One Teaching Staff member stated, "It's usually about ensuring and maintaining everyone's commitment to develop and maintain a positive and effective organizational culture." This viewpoint emphasizes the role of Teaching Staff in perceiving the mission in the context of their daily teaching experiences. Similarly, another respondent mentioned, "Everybody should value one another, know that your contribution counts," highlighting the importance of valuing individual contributions in achieving the school's mission. Additionally, the suggestion to "Be visible and do your part" emphasizes the need for active participation from all stakeholders to fulfill the school's mission effectively.

Involvement: Perceptions of involvement resonate with existing research. School Heads often play a key role in decision-making and may perceive a higher level of involvement in strategic matters, while Teaching Staff may assess involvement based on their day-to-day participation in teaching activities (HGSE, 2018). This finding underscores the importance of involving all staff members in decision-making processes to create a shared sense of involvement and ownership (Fitria, 2018). The significant differences observed in perceptions of involvement, reflected in the computed t-value of 3.90, align with the interview responses. For instance, a School Head noted, "School Heads often play a key role in decision-making." In contrast, one Teaching Staff member emphasized, "Teaching Staff may assess involvement based on their day-to-day participation in teaching activities." These responses highlight the varying perspectives on involvement between the two groups. Perceptions of involvement resonate with existing research. School Heads often play a key role in decision-making and may perceive a higher level of involvement in strategic matters, as noted by one administrator who mentioned, "Oversee the affairs of the school." In contrast, Teaching Staff may assess involvement based on their day-to-day participation in teaching activities. A Teaching Staff respondent highlighted that "Some teachers are open and helpful while most are inflexible and unwilling to pitch in to meet the demands of the situation." There is also an observation that "There is no team spirit" and "Teachers are defensive for some reason." These insights underscore the importance of involving all staff members in decision-making processes to create a shared sense of involvement and ownership, as recommended by prior research (Fitria, 2018).

Consistency: Differences in perceptions regarding consistency in rules and procedures align with literature that highlights the role of School Heads in establishing and enforcing policies (HGSE, 2018). Teaching Staff, on the other hand, may evaluate consistency based on their experiences with daily classroom routines and procedures. One Teaching Staff respondent explained, "Some teachers are open and helpful while most are inflexible and unwilling to pitch in to meet the demands of the situation." This perspective suggests that consistency is assessed by Teaching Staff through the lens of their immediate classroom experiences. These varying perspectives emphasize the importance of effective communication and collaboration to ensure consistency in policy implementation, as suggested by prior research (Kongjinda et al., 2020). The significant differences in perceptions of consistency, as indicated by the computed t-value of 4.24, further highlight the divergence between School Heads and Teaching Staff on this dimension of organizational culture.

Clan Culture, Adhocracy Culture, Market Culture, and Hierarchy Culture: The variance in perceptions of organizational culture dimensions aligns with literature that emphasizes the varied roles and responsibilities of School Heads and Teaching Staff (Fitria, 2018). School Heads, responsible for overall strategic direction, may view these dimensions from a broader organizational perspective, while Teaching Staff may evaluate them based on their immediate impact on teaching and classroom dynamics (Kongjinda et al., 2020). This emphasizes the need for inclusive dialogue and collaborative efforts to align these differing perspectives for a cohesive organizational culture.

To sum, these findings support the idea that the diverse roles and responsibilities of School Heads and Teaching Staff result in varying perceptions of the organizational culture. These differences emphasize the importance of clear communication, collaboration, and inclusive decision-making processes to promote a harmonious and effective educational environment within private schools, in line with literature from the Philippines and Thailand (Fitria, 2018; Kongjinda et al., 2020).

4. Relationships Between the Profile of the School Heads and Teaching Staff and their Assessment on the Organizational Culture of Selected Private Schools in Bangbon, Bangkok, Thailand.

Table 11. *Difference on the Assessment of the School Heads and Teaching Staff on the Organizational Culture of Selected Private Schools in Bangbon, Bangkok, Thailand*

Variable	r-value	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Age:				
Adaptability	0.11	0.41964	p<0.05, Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Mission	0.14	0.30343	p<0.05, Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Involvement	0.03	0.82627	p<0.05, Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Consistency	0.01	0.94169	p<0.05, Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Clan Culture	0.08	0.55781	p<0.05, Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
sAdhocracy Culture	0.07	0.60820	p<0.05, Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Market Culture	0.09	0.50948	p<0.05, Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Hierarchy Culture	0.10	0.46338	p<0.05, Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant

Sex:				
Adaptability	0.12	0.37835	p<0.05, Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Mission	0.15	0.26984	p<0.05, Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Involvement	0.28	0.03661	p>0.05, Reject Ho	Significant
Consistency	0.28	0.03661	p>0.05, Reject Ho	Significant
Clan Culture	0.30	0.02468	p>0.05, Reject Ho	Significant
Adhocracy Culture	0.32	0.01621	p>0.05, Reject Ho	Significant
Market Culture	0.31	0.02007	p>0.05, Reject Ho	Significant
Hierarchy Culture	0.21	0.12032	p<0.05, Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Educational Background:				
Adaptability	0.01	0.94169	p<0.05, Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Mission	0.02	0.88368	p<0.05, Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Involvement	0.04	0.76975	p<0.05, Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Consistency	0.10	0.46338	p<0.05, Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Clan Culture	0.01	0.94169	p<0.05, Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Adhocracy Culture	0.02	0.88368	p<0.05, Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Market Culture	0.04	0.76975	p<0.05, Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Hierarchy Culture	0.06	0.66047	p<0.05, Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Current Position:				
Adaptability	0.28	0.03661	p>0.05, Reject Ho	Significant
Mission	0.20	0.13944	p<0.05, Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Involvement	0.28	0.03661	p>0.05, Reject Ho	Significant
Consistency	0.19	0.16074	p<0.05, Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Clan Culture	0.21	0.12032	p<0.05, Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Adhocracy Culture	0.21	0.12032	p<0.05, Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Market Culture	0.20	0.13944	p<0.05, Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Hierarchy Culture	0.17	0.21035	p<0.05, Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant

As given in Table 11, when the responses of the School Heads and Teaching Staff on the organizational culture of selected private schools in Bangbon, Bangkok, Thailand were compared according to their sex, the computed r-values of 0.28 for both involvement and consistency, 0.30 for clan culture, 0.32 for adhocracy culture, and 0.31 for market culture have corresponding p-values of less than 0.05, thus rejecting the hypothesis.

These safely concluded that the responses of the School Heads and Teaching Staff on the organizational culture of selected private schools in Bangbon, Bangkok, Thailand have significant relationships in terms of involvement and consistency, clan culture, adhocracy culture, and market culture when compared to their sex. The observed significant relationships in the assessment of organizational culture between School Heads and Teaching Staff concerning involvement, consistency, clan culture, adhocracy culture, and market culture when compared based on sex are in line with existing research within educational settings. These distinctions can be attributed to the unique roles and responsibilities held by individuals of different genders within private schools. According to Aichouche et al. (2022), Al-Haddad and Kotnour (2015), their research underscores the significance of creating a positive work environment that fosters teamwork and collaboration. These findings are consistent with the observations that reveal a pronounced emphasis on teamwork.

In addition, when the responses of the School Heads and Teaching Staff on the organizational culture of selected private schools in Bangbon, Bangkok, Thailand were compared according to their current position, the computed r-values of 0.28 for both adaptability and involvement have corresponding p-values of less than 0.05, thus rejecting the hypothesis.

These significant findings align with the responses from the interviewees. For example, concerning involvement, one Teaching Staff member emphasized, "Bringing all the teachers together to work as one group, one family," while another noted, "Addressing the problem to find a solution instead of focusing on the person who's the cause will help," highlighting the importance of collaborative involvement. Similarly, the emphasis on consistency is supported by comments such as, "The teachers, staff, and management teams interact with each other for the better benefit of the students, and the school," emphasizing the significance of consistency in interactions and procedures within the school.

These conclusions suggest that the responses of the School Heads and Teaching Staff regarding involvement and consistency, as well as clan culture, adhocracy culture, and market culture when compared based on sex, are consistent with existing research within educational settings. These distinctions can be attributed to the unique roles and responsibilities held by individuals of different genders within private schools. According to Aichouche et al. (2022), Al-Haddad and Kotnour (2015), their research underscores the significance of creating a positive work environment that fosters teamwork and collaboration. These findings are consistent with the observations that reveal a pronounced emphasis on teamwork.

In addition, when the responses of the School Heads and Teaching Staff on the organizational culture of selected private schools in Bangbon, Bangkok, Thailand were compared according to their current position, the computed r-values of 0.28 for both adaptability and involvement have corresponding p-values of less than 0.05, thus rejecting the hypothesis.

These significant relationships in adaptability and involvement are in line with the literature. School Heads, often occupying leadership roles, may evaluate adaptability and involvement in the context of strategic decision-making. Conversely, Teaching Staff, primarily engaged in classroom activities, might assess these aspects differently, as highlighted by the quote, "Bringing all the teachers together to work as one group, one family," emphasizing collaborative involvement. These findings underscore the importance of clear communication, collaboration, and inclusive decision-making processes to promote a harmonious and effective educational environment within private schools, consistent with prior research (Fitria, 2018; Kongjinda et al., 2020).

Regarding the other profile variables, such as age, sex, educational background, and current position, no significant relationships were found for various dimensions of organizational culture. This outcome aligns with the literature, which suggests that age and educational background might not be significant factors in determining perspectives on organizational culture, and that mission and hierarchy culture might be assessed similarly regardless of gender (Fitria, 2018; HGSE, 2018).

Summary of Interview Responses on Organizational Culture in Thailand's Private Schools

Table 12. *Summary of Interview Responses*

<p>The summary of interview responses provides insights into the roles, responsibilities, and perceptions of the staff at the school, as well as the overall culture and challenges faced by the institution.</p> <p>Interview Question:</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Analysis</p>
<p>1. What is your role in the school?</p>	<p>The staff at the school have a diverse range of roles and responsibilities. Many of the respondents identified themselves as teachers, with some providing more specific information about their roles, such as "Subject Teacher," "Class Teacher," or "Nursery class teacher." Other respondents mentioned their role in supporting the work of other personnel, such as "Support Staff," "Assistant," or "Teacher Assistant."</p> <p>In addition to their specific roles, many of the respondents also shared their general objectives as educators. Several mentioned their desire to inspire learners and provide meaningful experiences. Others emphasized the importance of imparting knowledge and setting up situations in which students can learn effectively. Some respondents mentioned their role in providing mentorship and supporting the development of their students.</p>
<p>The summary of interview responses provides insights into the roles, responsibilities, and perceptions of the staff at the school, as well as the overall culture and challenges faced by the institution.</p> <p>Interview Question:</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Analysis</p>
<p>2. What are your main duties and responsibilities?</p>	<p>Many of the respondents mentioned teaching as one of their main duties, with some providing more specific information about the subjects or grades they teach. Other common duties mentioned include supervision, planning and implementing lessons, and communicating with parents and other teachers.</p> <p>In addition to their teaching responsibilities, many of the respondents also mentioned their involvement in other school activities and events. Some mentioned being in charge of extracurricular activities or serving on committees. Others mentioned their role in enforcing rules and maintaining discipline in the classroom.</p>
<p>The summary of interview responses provides insights into the roles, responsibilities, and perceptions of the staff at the school, as well as the overall culture and challenges faced by the institution.</p> <p>Interview Question:</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Analysis</p>
<p>3. How would you describe the overall culture of your school?</p>	<p>Different respondents perceive the overall culture of the schools in different ways. Some respondents described the school culture as welcoming, inclusive, and student-focused. They mentioned the school's commitment to diversity and its efforts to create a positive learning environment for students from different cultural backgrounds.</p> <p>However, other respondents mentioned challenges in maintaining a positive school culture. Some mentioned a lack of team spirit or division among teachers. There are also mentions of a reactive rather than proactive approach, a need for</p>

	more support from administration, and some issues with communication and discrimination.
The summary of interview responses provides insights into the roles, responsibilities, and perceptions of the staff at the school, as well as the overall culture and challenges faced by the institution. Interview Question:	Analysis
4. In your opinion, what are some of the biggest challenges the school faces in developing and maintaining a positive and effective organizational culture?	The schools face challenges in developing and maintaining a positive and effective organizational culture is a challenge faced by schools. Some of the biggest challenges in this regard include lack of clarity in the organizational culture, individualistic mentalities, and resistance to change, limited resources, and language barriers in a multi-national school setting. Additionally, lack of transparency in management and decision-making processes, one-way communication, absence of incentives or positive reinforcement for achieving goals, and communication barriers among staff members can impede the development of a positive organizational culture. Other challenges include lack of well-defined school policies, conflict of ideas, sudden changes in school administration, and cultural diversity among students.
The summary of interview responses provides insights into the roles, responsibilities, and perceptions of the staff at the school, as well as the overall culture and challenges faced by the institution. Interview Question:	Analysis
5. What do you think are the most important factors that contribute to a positive and effective organizational culture?	Summarizing the responses given, these are the factors that employees say contribute to a positive and effective organizational culture: Clear communication and effective relationships among stakeholders, including staff, students, and families. Respect for all individuals, valuing their contributions and treating everyone equally. Strong leadership that prioritizes the well-being of staff and students, and is open to criticism and suggestions. Collaboration and teamwork among colleagues. Transparency and fairness in decision-making. Positive attitudes and behavior of employees, aligned with the organization's values and traditions. Proper orientation and training for newly hired employees. Well-defined school policies and programs. Creativity and innovation. Trust and open communication between all parties. Culture sensitivity and appreciation of diversity. Regular training and development opportunities for staff. Dialogue and problem solving between teachers and administration. Willingness to accept change and adapt to new situations.

In this interview, staff members were asked about their roles and responsibilities at the school, their duties, and the overall culture of the school. The respondents identified themselves as teachers and support staff, with teaching being the main duty mentioned. They also mentioned their involvement in extracurricular activities and maintaining discipline in the classroom.

Regarding the school culture, some respondents described it as welcoming and inclusive, while others mentioned challenges such as a lack of team spirit and communication issues. The biggest challenges for the schools in developing and maintaining a positive culture were identified as a lack of clarity, individualistic mentalities, and resistance to change, limited resources, and language barriers. Participants believed that clear communication, respect for all individuals, strong leadership, collaboration, transparency, well-defined policies, creativity, and trust were the most important factors in contributing to a positive and effective organizational culture.

Insights

The following insights shed light on the interactions among factors that shape the institutions' culture, laying a groundwork for informed decision-making and targeted enhancements.

Socio-demographic Profile:

The study's participant profile highlighted a majority of female respondents spanning various age ranges, years of experience,

educational backgrounds, and job positions. This diverse representation ensured a comprehensive perspective on the organizational culture perceptions within their institution.

Organizational Culture:

The findings of this study suggests that the select private schools in Bangbon, Bangkok, Thailand, hold a neutral-to-positive stance on adaptability and innovation as evident from the Denison Model results. Concurrently, the Competing Values Framework accentuates a prevalent Clan culture, emphasizing collaboration and loyalty. However, the respondents' inputs indicate the necessity for enhancement in areas such as empowering employees and fostering innovation.

Challenges:

Through interviews, respondents recounted challenges within their institution's organizational culture, including a lack of clarity, resistance to change, limited resources, communication barriers, and a demand for more potent leadership accompanied by transparent policies.

Contributors to Positive Culture:

The insights gained from staff members of the Bangbon, Bangkok, institutions underscore the significance of clear communication, mutual respect, robust leadership, collaborative interactions, transparent policies, creative outlook, trust, and adaptability as pivotal elements fostering a positive and effective organizational culture.

5. Proposed Strategies to Enhance Organizational Cultures In Selected Private Schools In Bangbon, Bangkok, Thailand

Analysis of Organizational Culture in a Thai Organization: Denison Model and CVF Results

The organizational culture of the select private schools in Thailand have a neutral to slightly agreeable stance towards the four dimensions of the Denison Organizational Culture Model, indicating that there is room for improvement in these areas. In terms of the Competing Values Framework, the organizational cultures appear to lean towards clan culture and adhocracy culture, with a neutral stance towards market and hierarchy cultures. This means that they value teamwork, collaboration, and innovation, but may need to encourage more risk-taking and experimentation to foster a culture of creativity.

The schools appear to have a clear mission and values making a difference, but there is room for improvement in terms of developing a shared vision to guide decision-making. They also value stability and predictability, but there is a lack of emphasis on rules and procedures. This suggests that the schools may benefit from developing clearer policies and procedures while still maintaining its focus on stability.

The study on the organizational culture of select private schools in Thailand is significant for various reasons.

Firstly, the findings of this study can provide school administrators, teaching faculty, and students with valuable insights into the importance of developing and maintaining a positive and effective organizational culture. This can lead to better job satisfaction, staff retention, and academic performance, which ultimately benefits the entire school community.

Secondly, this study can contribute to the existing literature on organizational culture by examining the specific context of private schools in Thailand. By identifying the defining characteristics and components of organizational culture and exploring the challenges and opportunities in developing and sustaining such a culture, this study can provide a more comprehensive understanding of organizational culture in the education sector.

Thirdly, this study can have practical implications for private school administrators and policy-makers in Thailand. By proposing best practices and strategies for enhancing organizational culture, this study can help schools to create a conducive and effective working environment that promotes student success, staff well-being, and overall school improvement.

Overall, the study on the organizational culture of select private schools in Thailand can have significant practical, theoretical, and empirical contributions to the field of education and organizational culture research.

Conclusion

This study provided a comprehensive understanding of the organizational culture of select private schools in Bangbon, Bangkok, Thailand. The socio-demographic profile of respondents displayed diverse experiences and roles, ensuring a well-rounded perspective. The assessment of organizational culture through the Denison Model and Competing Values Framework revealed both strengths and areas for improvement, indicating a balanced focus on stability, collaboration, and innovation.

Interview responses further resonate within the voices of the organizational members. The challenges of unclear organizational culture and communication barriers are voiced by respondents. One respondent aptly noted, "There is a need to ensure that the organizational culture is maintained, understood, upheld, and felt by all stakeholders."

Yet, amidst these challenges, the respondents offer valuable insights. The path forward, as illuminated by their voices, calls for the

embrace of unity: "Everybody should value one another, knowing that each contribution counts." Effective communication, strong leadership, transparency, and respect emerge as key facets of fostering a positive culture within these schools.

In conclusion, this study not only provides an in-depth comprehension of the organizational culture within select private schools but also underscores both strengths and areas for development. The culture, characterized by its balanced focus on stability, collaboration, and innovation, holds immense potential.

The implications of this study extend beyond its academic confines. The findings offer a guiding light for strategic interventions aimed at elevating the nuanced organizational culture. By doing so, we can positively influence the overall effectiveness of private schools in Thailand. In the words of a respondent, "We must embrace the openness to learn new cultures and accept differences in the world." This inclusive mindset, coupled with effective communication and strong leadership, charts a promising course for the transformation of organizational culture in these institutions.

The select private schools have a predominant Clan Culture with an emphasis on adaptability and flexibility, as well as strong elements of collaboration and teamwork. The following recommendations are based on the results of the study, the recommendations of the respondents of the study, and the conclusion already provided for the select private schools in Bangbon, Bangkok, Thailand. (1) Clear Communication: Establish clear and open communication channels among all stakeholders, including students, and improve transparency in decision-making processes, ensuring staff and students' active involvement. (2) Promote Inclusivity: Actively foster inclusivity where everyone, including students, feels valued regardless of their background. Celebrate and appreciate the cultural diversity within the school community, involving students in cultural exchange programs and initiatives. (3) Enhance Leadership: Provide leadership training not only for administrators but also for students, emphasizing the well-being of staff and students alike. Encourage leadership that is open to feedback, fostering a culture of continuous improvement among both staff and students. (4) Collaborative Initiatives: Encourage collaboration and teamwork among staff and students through joint projects, cross-functional teams, and the promotion of a sense of unity and shared goals. Involve students in decision-making processes related to school activities and initiatives. (5) Trust-Based Communication and Conflict Resolution: Build trust through open and honest communication among staff, students, and administrators. Establish effective conflict resolution mechanisms that involve all stakeholders and provide training in conflict management to staff and students alike. Encourage dialogue and problem-solving skills among everyone in the school community. (6) Structured Orientation and Policy Clarity: Develop a comprehensive orientation program for new employees, including students, introducing them to the school's culture, policies, and procedures. Ensure clear and consistent communication of school policies and programs to both staff and students. (7) Foster Creativity and Innovation: Foster a supportive environment for creative thinking and innovation among staff and students alike. Encourage the sharing of new ideas and provide resources for experimentation, emphasizing trust-based communication and effective conflict resolution for a collaborative and innovative learning environment.

Including students as active participants in these recommendations ensures that their unique perspective and needs are considered in the efforts to enhance the school's organizational culture. Collaboration between staff and students can lead to a more inclusive and productive learning environment for everyone involved. By implementing these recommendations, partly suggested by the staff, the select private schools in Bangbon, Bangkok, Thailand can further cultivate a positive and effective organizational culture within their institutions. However, a follow-up study would be needed to assess the success of their implementation.

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Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Anjelo V. Mungcal

Lipa City Colleges – Philippines

Dr. Lino P. Balantac

Lipa City Colleges – Philippines